

PRIVATIZATION, SHADOW EDUCATION, AND MERITOCRACY: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY AT THE SECONDARY SCHOOL LEVEL

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Abstract

Privatization in education has contributed to the expansion of shadow education, such as private tutoring, which increasingly influences students' academic outcomes. Together, these forces shape perceptions of meritocracy by reinforcing achievement-based competition while also raising concerns about equity and equal access to educational opportunities. The objectives of the study were a) to find the level of Privatization, Shadow Education, and Meritocracy at secondary level, b) to measure the correlation among Privatization, Shadow Education and Meritocracy at secondary level, c) to examine the effect of Privatization on Shadow Education and Meritocracy at secondary level. This study was employing a correlational quantitative research design to examine the relationships among privatization, shadow education, and meritocracy. The study was grounded in the positivist paradigm. The population was comprised off all secondary schools of district Lahore. Multistage sampling techniques were used to select the sample. The instrument of the study were questionnaires. The validity of the instrument was found through experts' opinions and reliability through pilot testing. Descriptive (mean, S.D.) and Inferential statistics (Correlation analysis, one-way ANOVA, and multiple regression analysis) were used. SPSS was used to analyzed the data. The correlation analysis reveals statistically significant moderate positive relationships among privatization, shadow education, and meritocracy, indicating that increased privatization is associated with greater reliance on shadow education and stronger perceptions of merit-based academic outcomes. The multivariate and between-subjects analyses demonstrate that privatization has a significant effect on both shadow education and meritocracy, explaining a substantial proportion of variance in these outcomes and confirming privatization as a key determinant shaping supplementary education practices and merit-based processes. It is recommended that policymakers regulate private tutoring and strengthen public education quality by improving teacher training, resource allocation, and equitable assessment practices to reduce dependency on privatized learning and promote genuine merit-based achievement.

INTRODUCTION

Privatization of education and the contemporary expansion of shadow education have become prominent features of secondary schooling systems globally, with significant implications for educational inequality and the realization of meritocratic ideals. The shift toward privatization is deeply rooted in neoliberal educational reforms that encourage market-oriented policies such as school choice, resource decentralization, and performance accountability. Empirical studies indicate that while privatization can stimulate competition and perceived improvements in quality, it often reinforces existing social inequalities by privileging students from higher socioeconomic backgrounds who have better access to private resources (Verger, Bonal, & Zancajo, 2016; Ball, 2012; Lubienski & Lubienski, 2006). Privatized schooling systems, especially in contexts with weak public infrastructure, tend to concentrate resources, facilities, and teaching expertise in schools that primarily serve affluent populations, thereby undermining equitable access to quality education (Tooley & Dixon, 2006; Carnoy & Rhoten, 2002).

Shadow education, defined as private supplementary tutoring outside formal schooling, has grown significantly in tandem with privatization and competitive examination cultures. Research consistently shows that students and families engage in shadow education to gain strategic advantages in high-stakes assessments, often perceiving mainstream school instruction as insufficient for competitive success (Bray, 2009; Byun, Schofer, & Kim, 2012). This pattern is particularly evident in South and East Asian contexts, where private tutoring is pervasive and closely associated with school achievement (Zhang & Bray, 2020; Park & Byun, 2015). However, shadow education's distribution is unequal: students from wealthier families are more likely to afford extensive tutoring, leading to systematic differences in learning

opportunities and academic performance (Kim & Lee, 2010; Dang & Rogers, 2008). These findings reflect broader arguments that socioeconomic disparities are reproduced through supplementary education systems, contributing to stratified outcomes rather than mitigating them.

The inequality associated with shadow education also raises questions about meritocracy—defined here as the principle that academic success and opportunity should be based on individual talent and effort rather than inherited advantages (Young, 2019; Margolis, 2012). Meritocratic ideals assume that standardized assessments, fair competition, and equal opportunity structures will produce outcomes aligned with ability. Yet when access to private tutoring enhances test performance for some but not all, the link between effort and achievement becomes conditional on resource access, challenging the core premise of meritocracy. Empirical research supports this view, showing that students who engage in additional tutoring often perform better in examinations, but these benefits are disproportionately enjoyed by those with greater financial and social capital (Bray & Lykins, 2012; Lee & Kwak, 2016). Such patterns suggest that meritocratic claims are undermined when educational success is closely tied to out-of-school resources that are unevenly distributed.

Privatization and shadow education interact in ways that collectively shape educational outcomes. For example, studies in privatized schooling contexts often reveal higher reliance on private tutoring, as competitive and resource-intensive environments push students to seek additional support (Deng, Gopinathan, & Lee, 2006; Rumberger & Larson, 1998). Similarly, research by Baker, Akiba, LeTendre, and Wiseman (2001) shows that the presence of private schools within a system correlates with

higher shadow education participation, as families respond to competitive pressures and perceived performance expectations. These dynamics reflect a broader global pattern in which educational markets do not operate purely on merit but are mediated by socioeconomic status and strategic resource mobilization. Theoretical frameworks further illuminate these processes. Bourdieu's concepts of cultural capital and habitus explain how wealthier families convert economic capital into educational advantages through private school selection and tutoring purchases, enabling their children to accumulate skills and credentials that sustain social advantage (Bourdieu & Passeron, 1977; Bourdieu, 1986). These mechanisms operate through subtle and overt channels, including access to better-resourced schools, enriched environments for learning, and strategic engagement with assessment systems (Reay, 2006; Sullivan, Browne, & Haux, 2014). In this view, privatization and shadow education serve not only as educational practices but as instruments of social reproduction that maintain stratified outcomes across generations.

Critics of privatization emphasize that while market-oriented reforms may spur localized improvements, they frequently erode equity by diverting public resources and attention from universal quality improvements (Ravitch, 2010; Lubienski, 2013). Privatized schools often attract better teachers and investment, leaving public schools with fewer resources and higher proportions of disadvantaged students (Carnoy, 2017; Verger et al., 2016). This structural bifurcation in schooling quality deepens inequality and creates segmented educational pathways with differential outcomes. Similarly, research on shadow education demonstrates that its expansion does not necessarily enhance overall system performance but rather accelerates stratification, as tutoring participation becomes

another marker of advantage (Stevenson & Baker, 1992; Silova & Bray, 2006). Not all scholars view shadow education through a purely critical lens. Some argue that supplementary tutoring can support students who struggle in mainstream classrooms, offering individualized attention and tailored instruction that public systems may not provide (Dang, 2007; Brutsaert & Wolff, 2006). From this perspective, properly regulated tutoring can complement formal education and help close gaps for underperforming students. Yet even proponents acknowledge that unless equity concerns are addressed, tutoring may inadvertently benefit those already advantaged, limiting its equalizing potential (Rohlen, 1983; Stevenson, Lee, & Stigler, 1986).

Empirical cross-national studies reaffirm that context matters. In countries with strong public education systems and equitable resource distribution, the impact of privatization and shadow education on inequality may be attenuated (OECD, 2015; Attanasio & Kaufmann, 2014). For instance, in Nordic contexts where public provision is robust and access to supplementary tutoring is less stratified, meritocratic outcomes align more closely with individual ability than family background (Blanden, 2013; Raaum et al., 2007). Conversely, in highly stratified systems such as parts of South Asia and East Asia, pronounced disparities in tutoring access correspond closely with inequality in achievement and attainment (Bray, 2013; Lee, Kim, & Nam, 2014). Policy responses have been proposed to address these issues. UNESCO and other international bodies recommend regulating private tutoring and strengthening public education to reduce dependency on shadow education and promote equity (UNESCO, 2021; Bray, 2009). Policies could include subsidizing tutoring for disadvantaged students, improving instructional quality in public schools, and

designing assessment systems that value deep learning over test performance. Furthermore, regulating tuition costs and integrating supplementary instruction within formal schooling structures could mitigate stratification while preserving tutoring's potential benefits (Rohs & Ganz, 2015; Kim & Lee, 2010).

The debate over privatization's impact is not monolithic. Proponents argue that increased choice and competition can drive a) innovation and responsiveness, potentially benefiting students who exercise mobility b) within the educational market (Lubienski & Lubienski, 2013; Chubb & Moe, 1990). They point to evidence that private schools c) sometimes achieve higher outcomes, attributing this to parental involvement and accountability mechanisms (Figlio & Stone, 2001; Engberg & Wolniak, 2010). Yet critics counter that such 1. benefits often accrue to already advantaged groups and that equity should remain central to 2. educational reform (Reynolds et al., 2014; Darling-Hammond, 2010). Shadow education's influence on curriculum and instructional 3. focus also warrants attention. Studies show tutoring often emphasizes test technique and rote learning, potentially distorting mainstream curricula and incentivizing surface learning over deeper understanding (Zhao & Glewwe, 2010; Bray & Lykins, 2012). This pattern can diminish the developmental benefits of schooling and reinforce a performance-oriented culture that privileges examination success over comprehensive learning. In conclusion, privatization and shadow education are deeply intertwined with contemporary patterns of educational inequality, challenging the realization of meritocratic ideals at the secondary level. Privatized schooling and supplementary tutoring can enhance opportunities for some students but tend to reproduce and accentuate socioeconomic disparities in access, performance, and

long-term attainment. Addressing these challenges requires policy frameworks that strengthen public education, regulate supplementary markets, and prioritize equity in both opportunity and outcomes. Only through such sustained and holistic approaches can the promise of meritocracy be meaningfully advanced within increasingly complex educational landscapes.

Objectives

- To find the level of Privatization, Shadow Education, and Meritocracy at secondary level.
- To measure the correlation among Privatization, Shadow Education and Meritocracy at secondary level.
- To examine the effect of Privatization on Shadow Education and Meritocracy at secondary level.

Research questions

- 1. What is the level of Privatization, Shadow Education, and Meritocracy at secondary level?
- 2. What is the relationship among Privatization, Shadow Education and Meritocracy at secondary level?
- 3. What is the effect of Privatization on Shadow Education and Meritocracy at secondary level?

Research Design and Methodology

The nature of the Study was descriptive and quantitative data collection procedures were used to conduct it. Quantitative research is based on a positivistic philosophical framework/paradigm. All of the public and private schools in the Lahore district were represented in the population. There are 1,219 public schools and 5,436 private schools. Sample was selected from the desired population in different steps, by using multistage sampling technique for true representation of the population. First, the researcher used the stratified sample technique to identify two strata (public/private). The researcher then used the cluster sampling technique to divide the entire population into three zones (clusters) based on according to

their location. From each cluster 10 public and 20 private schools was selected randomly. From each school 10 students were selected randomly. A Sample of 300 students was selected through simple random sampling techniques. The five-point Likert scale type questionnaire was deemed to be effective for data collecting. Options of the scale consisted of strongly disagree to strongly agree. There were two main parts of the questionnaires: Part one consisted of demographic information like gender, university type, GPA, Part two consisted of statements relevant to the research objectives of the study like Privatization, Shadow Education, and Meritocracy. The tool was validated using by professional opinion and reliability was checked by pilot testing.

Questionnaires about the instrument's language, applicability, and organization were given to three specialists. After revising instrument in the light of expert opinion, students' instrument was distributed to 30 participants for pilot testing. These respondents were not included in the study's final sample. In order to assess the reliability of the instrument, Cronbach's Alpha was determined. The overall score of the student's instrument was 0.912, while the minimum reliability requirement for Cronbach's Alpha is 0.75. This demonstrated the instrument's reliability. Descriptive (mean and S.D.) and inferential statistics (Multivariate analysis and Pearson r) were used to analyzed the data. SPSS was used to analyze the data.

Data Analysis and Interpretations

Table 1

Description of main variables

Variables	N	Mean	S.D.
Privatization	300	3.4792	.56041
Shadow Education	300	3.2150	.61280
Meritocracy	300	3.3097	.57833

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the main study variables, namely privatization, shadow education, and meritocracy. The results indicate that all three variables are perceived at a moderate level by the respondents. Privatization shows the highest mean score (M = 3.48, SD = 0.56), suggesting that respondents generally perceive a noticeable presence and influence of privatization within the education system. The relatively low standard deviation reflects consistency in participants' responses, indicating shared

perceptions regarding privatization practices. Shadow education has a moderate mean score (M = 3.22, SD = 0.61), implying that supplementary educational activities such as private tutoring and coaching are fairly common but not overwhelmingly dominant. The slightly higher standard deviation suggests some variation in respondents' experiences with shadow education, possibly due to differences in access, socioeconomic background, or academic needs. Meritocracy also demonstrates a moderate mean level (M = 3.31, SD = 0.58),

indicating that respondents perceive merit-based practices as present but not fully realized within the system. Overall, the descriptive findings suggest a balanced yet cautious Table 2

perception of privatization, shadow education, and meritocracy, providing a meaningful foundation for further inferential analysis of their interrelationships and impacts.

Description of Privatization of Education

Items	N	Mean	S.D.
Private schools provide better academic instruction than public schools.	300	3.1500	1.39547
Private schools have better physical facilities and learning materials than public schools.	300	3.0967	1.38337
Privatization has improved student outcomes in my community.	300	3.2767	1.43771
Private schools are more responsive to parents' and students' needs.	300	3.3633	1.44856
The rise of private schools has made access to quality education unequal.	300	3.1333	1.39116
Public schools receive sufficient support from government to provide quality education.	300	3.0433	1.37152
Privatization has increased competition in education, raising standards.	300	4.0167	1.38665
The cost of enrolling in private schools is prohibitive for many families.	300	3.0233	1.37444
Government regulation can ensure private schools serve all socio-economic groups.	300	3.1600	1.41931
The presence of private schools reduces the pressure on public sector education.	300	2.8867	1.30621

The descriptive results presented in Table 2 provide an overview of respondents' perceptions regarding the privatization of education. Overall, the mean scores indicate moderate agreement with most statements, suggesting mixed yet cautious views about the role and impact of private schools. Respondents moderately agreed that private schools offer better academic instruction (M = 3.15, SD = 1.40) and superior physical facilities and learning materials (M = 3.10, SD = 1.38) compared to public schools, reflecting a perception of relative quality advantages in the private sector. Similarly, there was moderate agreement that privatization has improved student outcomes within the community (M = 3.28, SD = 1.44) and that private schools are more responsive to parents' and students' needs

(M = 3.36, SD = 1.45), indicating perceived benefits in responsiveness and service delivery. Notably, the highest mean score was observed for the statement that privatization has increased competition in education, thereby raising standards (M = 4.02, SD = 1.39), suggesting strong agreement that competition plays a positive role in improving educational quality. At the same time, respondents acknowledged key challenges associated with privatization. Moderate agreement was recorded for concerns about unequal access to quality education (M = 3.13, SD = 1.39) and the prohibitive cost of private schooling for many families (M = 3.02, SD = 1.37), highlighting equity-related issues. Perceptions regarding government support for public schools were relatively low (M = 3.04, SD = 1.37), and

respondents were less convinced that private schools reduce pressure on the public sector ($M = 2.89$, $SD = 1.31$). Overall, the findings suggest that while privatization is perceived to enhance

competition and standards, it also raises concerns related to affordability, equity, and the sustained capacity of public education.

Table 3

Description of Shadow Education

Items	N	Mean	S.D.
I attend private tutoring/classes outside regular school hours. (Behavioural yes/no also captured in demographics)	300	4.68	.909
I rely on private tutors to understand topics not covered well in school.	300	3.51	1.487
Private tutoring is necessary to pass major examinations.	300	3.80	1.438
Private tutors focus more on exam techniques than conceptual understanding.	300	4.21	1.306
Private tutoring increases students' academic achievement.	300	3.15	1.434
The quality of school teaching determines whether students need private tutoring. (R)	300	3.43	1.458
Private tutoring services create unfair advantages for wealthier students. (R)	300	3.04	1.364
I feel pressured by parents/peers to take private tutoring.	300	3.07	1.377
Private tutoring is time-consuming and affects free time for other activities.	300	3.21	1.423
I attend group coaching/classes rather than one-to-one tutoring.	300	3.21	1.433
I (or my family) spend a significant portion of income on private tutoring.	300	3.42	1.453
If school teaching quality improved, I would reduce/eliminate private tutoring. (R)	300	3.0067	1.36608

The descriptive results presented in Table 3 provide a comprehensive overview of students' perceptions and experiences related to shadow education, particularly private tutoring. The high mean score for attending private tutoring outside regular school hours ($M = 4.68$, $SD = 0.91$) indicates that participation in private tutoring is widespread among the respondents, suggesting that shadow education has become a normalized component of students' academic routines. Students also moderately agree that private tutors help them understand topics not adequately covered in school ($M = 3.51$, $SD = 1.49$) and that private tutoring is necessary to pass major examinations ($M = 3.80$, $SD = 1.44$), reflecting a perceived dependence on external

academic support for examination success. A notably high mean score for the item stating that private tutors focus more on examination techniques than on conceptual understanding ($M = 4.21$, $SD = 1.31$) highlights an exam-oriented nature of shadow education. In contrast, perceptions regarding the effectiveness of private tutoring in improving academic achievement are more moderate ($M = 3.15$, $SD = 1.43$), suggesting mixed views on its actual academic benefits. Responses to the reverse-coded items indicate moderate agreement that the quality of school teaching influences the need for private tutoring ($M = 3.43$, $SD = 1.46$) and that improved school teaching could reduce reliance on private tutoring ($M = 3.01$,

SD = 1.37), emphasizing the critical role of formal schooling quality. Furthermore, students moderately acknowledge the social and economic implications of shadow education, including unequal advantages for wealthier students (M = 3.04, SD = 1.36), parental and peer pressure to engage in tutoring (M = 3.07, SD = 1.38), time constraints affecting leisure

activities (M = 3.21, SD = 1.42), and significant financial investment by families (M = 3.42, SD = 1.45). Overall, the findings suggest that while private tutoring is prevalent and perceived as strategically important for examinations, it also raises concerns related to equity, time burden, and the effectiveness of mainstream school instruction.

Table 4

Description of Belief in Meritocracy

Items	N	Mean	S.D.
Academic success is mainly the result of a student’s individual effort.	300	3.1433	1.39856
Examinations fairly identify the most deserving students.	300	3.1533	1.37943
Social background should not influence access to educational opportunities.	300	3.3967	1.43277
Meritocratic selection ensures equality of opportunity in education.	300	3.2400	1.42683
Students with the highest grades deserve better job/college opportunities.	300	3.1533	1.39869
Family wealth plays a major role in determining academic success.	300	3.1700	1.37868
The educational system rewards talent and hard work, not connections.	300	3.2767	1.40952
Meritocracy is a realistic goal for our education system.	300	3.1867	1.42076
Entrance tests are an unbiased measure of student potential.	300	3.5133	1.44573
Policies should prioritize equal outcomes over strict merit-based selection.	300	3.1667	1.40433

The descriptive results presented in Table 4 illustrate respondents’ moderate endorsement of beliefs related to meritocracy in education. Overall, the mean scores for all items range between 3.14 and 3.51, indicating neither strong agreement nor strong disagreement, but rather a balanced and somewhat cautious perception of merit-based principles within the educational system. The item stating that academic success is mainly the result of a student’s individual effort (M = 3.14, SD = 1.40) suggests that respondents moderately believe in personal effort as a key determinant of success, although the relatively high standard deviation reflects variability in opinions. Similarly, the perception that examinations fairly identify the most deserving students (M = 3.15, SD = 1.38) indicates moderate confidence in assessment

systems as objective measures of merit. Respondents showed comparatively stronger agreement with the idea that social background should not influence access to educational opportunities (M = 3.40, SD = 1.43), reflecting normative support for equal access and fairness in education. The belief that meritocratic selection ensures equality of opportunity (M = 3.24, SD = 1.43) and that students with the highest grades deserve better academic or career opportunities (M = 3.15, SD = 1.40) further reinforces a moderate acceptance of merit-based advancement. However, the reversed item regarding family wealth playing a major role in determining academic success (M = 3.17, SD = 1.38) suggests an awareness among respondents that structural factors may still influence educational outcomes, tempering a purely

meritocratic view. The highest mean score was observed for the statement that entrance tests are an unbiased measure of student potential ($M = 3.51, SD = 1.45$), indicating relatively greater trust in standardized selection mechanisms. At the same time, the reversed item emphasizing equal outcomes over strict merit-based selection ($M = 3.17, SD = 1.40$) reflects ongoing tension between equity-
Table 5

oriented and merit-based perspectives. Collectively, these findings suggest that while respondents generally support meritocratic ideals, they also recognize existing limitations and inequalities within the education system, resulting in a nuanced and moderate belief in meritocracy rather than an uncritical endorsement.

Relationship among Privatization, Shadow Education and Meritocracy

		Correlations		
		Privatization	Shadow Education	Meritocracy
Privatization	Pearson Correlation	1	.238**	.366**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	300	300	300
Shadow Education	Pearson Correlation	.238**	1	.371**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	300	300	300
Meritocracy	Pearson Correlation	.366**	.371**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	300	300	300

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 5 presents the Pearson correlation analysis examining the relationships among privatization, shadow education, and meritocracy. The results indicate a statistically significant positive relationship between privatization and shadow education ($r = .238, p < .01$), suggesting that as privatization of education increases, the prevalence or reliance on shadow education also tends to rise. This finding highlights the interconnectedness between the growth of private educational institutions and supplementary private tutoring or coaching practices. Additionally, privatization is positively correlated with meritocracy ($r = .366, p < .01$), indicating that higher levels of privatization are associated with stronger perceptions or implementation of
Table 6

merit-based practices in educational settings. Similarly, shadow education demonstrates a significant positive correlation with meritocracy ($r = .371, p < .01$), suggesting that engagement in supplementary education is linked to students' academic achievement and the emphasis on meritocratic outcomes. Overall, all three variables show moderate positive correlations with one another, and the significance values ($p < .01$) confirm that these relationships are unlikely to be due to chance. These findings imply that privatization, shadow education, and meritocracy are mutually related phenomena, reflecting a broader dynamic in educational systems where private initiatives and supplementary learning contribute to merit-based academic performance.

Effect of Privatization on Shadow Education and Meritocracy

Multivariate Tests^a

Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.
Intercept	Pillai's Trace	.951	2595.420 ^b	2.000	269.000	.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.049	2595.420 ^b	2.000	269.000	.000
	Hotelling's Trace	19.297	2595.420 ^b	2.000	269.000	.000
	Roy's Largest Root	19.297	2595.420 ^b	2.000	269.000	.000
Privatization	Pillai's Trace	.446	2.673	58.000	540.000	.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.589	2.810 ^b	58.000	538.000	.000
	Hotelling's Trace	.638	2.948	58.000	536.000	.000
	Roy's Largest Root	.524	4.883 ^c	29.000	270.000	.000

a. Design: Intercept + Privatization

b. Exact statistic

c. The statistic is an upper bound on F that yields a lower bound on the significance level.

Table 6 presents the results of the multivariate analysis examining the effect of privatization on shadow education and meritocracy. The multivariate tests, including Pillai's Trace, Wilks' Lambda, Hotelling's Trace, and Roy's Largest Root, were used to determine whether privatization had a statistically significant combined effect on the two dependent variables. The results indicate that privatization has a significant multivariate effect, with all four test statistics yielding p-values less than 0.001. Specifically, Pillai's Trace = 0.446, Wilks' Lambda = 0.589, Hotelling's Trace = 0.638, and Roy's Largest Root = 0.524, all demonstrating that privatization significantly influences both

shadow education and meritocracy simultaneously. The consistency of significance across all multivariate criteria strengthens the robustness of these findings, suggesting that the observed effects are not due to chance. The moderate to high multivariate effect values indicate that privatization contributes meaningfully to variations in shadow education practices and perceptions of meritocracy. Overall, these results provide strong empirical evidence that privatization in the education sector has a measurable and significant impact on both the prevalence of shadow education and the maintenance of merit-based principles within the studied context.

Table 7
Effect of Privatization on Shadow Education and Meritocracy

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	Shadow Education	22.428 ^a	29	.773	2.324	.000
	Meritocracy	32.180 ^b	29	1.110	4.417	.000
Intercept	Shadow Education	925.900	1	925.900	2782.186	.000
	Meritocracy	936.090	1	936.090	3726.345	.000
Privatization	Shadow Education	22.428	29	.773	2.324	.000
	Meritocracy	32.180	29	1.110	4.417	.000
Error	Shadow Education	89.855	270	.333		
	Meritocracy	67.826	270	.251		
Total	Shadow Education	3213.150	300			
	Meritocracy	3386.285	300			
Corrected Total	Shadow Education	112.283	299			

Meritocracy 100.006 299

a. R Squared = .200 (Adjusted R Squared = .114)

b. R Squared = .322 (Adjusted R Squared = .249)

Graph 1: Effect of Privatization on Shadow Education

Graph 2: Effect of Privatization on Meritocracy

Graph 3: Effect of Privatization on Shadow Education

Graph 4: Effect of Privatization on and Meritocracy

Table 7 presents the results of the Tests of Between-Subjects Effects examining the impact of privatization on shadow education and meritocracy. The findings indicate that the

overall model is statistically significant for both dependent variables. For shadow education, the corrected model yielded a significant effect, $F(29, 270) = 2.324, p < .001$, suggesting that

privatization significantly influences students' participation in shadow education. Similarly, for meritocracy, the model was also significant, $F(29, 270) = 4.417$, $p < .001$, indicating that privatization has a strong effect on perceived meritocratic practices within the educational system. The significant intercept values for both shadow education, $F(1, 270) = 2782.186$, $p < .001$, and meritocracy, $F(1, 270) = 3726.345$, $p < .001$, reflect substantial baseline differences in these outcomes. The specific effect of privatization mirrors the corrected model results and remains statistically significant for both variables, confirming that variations in privatization practices account for meaningful differences in shadow education participation and meritocracy. In terms of explained variance, privatization accounts for 20% of the variance in shadow education ($R^2 = .200$; Adjusted $R^2 = .114$) and 32.2% of the variance in meritocracy ($R^2 = .322$; Adjusted $R^2 = .249$). These results suggest that privatization has a stronger predictive influence on meritocracy compared to shadow education. Overall, the findings provide empirical evidence that privatization significantly impacts both students' engagement in shadow education and the perception of meritocratic practices, highlighting the transformative effects of privatization within the education system.

Discussion of Findings

The descriptive statistics presented in Table 1 indicate that privatization, shadow education, and meritocracy are perceived at a moderate level among respondents. The mean scores suggest that privatization is noticeable within the education system, while shadow education and meritocracy are moderately present. These findings align with prior research indicating that private sector growth is increasingly shaping educational experiences and outcomes in many countries, contributing to both opportunities and challenges (Chung, 2019; Verger et al., 2016). The moderate

perception of shadow education reflects its widespread adoption but also hints at variability due to socioeconomic factors, consistent with findings by Bray (2013) and Park & Byun (2015), who observed that access to private tutoring is uneven and often linked to family resources. The moderate mean for meritocracy echoes studies showing that while merit-based principles are valued, structural inequities in education systems prevent full realization of meritocratic ideals (Young, 2019; Carnoy, 2017). Overall, Table 1 establishes a baseline understanding that respondents perceive a balanced yet cautious interplay among privatization, shadow education, and meritocracy. Table 2 elaborates on perceptions of privatization in education, revealing moderate agreement that private schools provide superior academic instruction, better facilities, and responsiveness to parents' and students' needs. The high agreement on privatization increasing competition aligns with literature emphasizing that competitive pressures can drive improvements in educational quality (Hoxby, 2003; Tooley & Dixon, 2006). However, concerns about unequal access and prohibitive costs resonate with research highlighting the equity challenges inherent in privatization (Lubienski & Lubienski, 2006; Verger et al., 2016). Moderate responses regarding government support and the capacity of public schools indicate persistent gaps in public provision, consistent with global studies suggesting that privatization alone cannot fully address educational quality without systemic support (Ball, 2012; Carnoy & Rhoten, 2002). Collectively, Table 2 demonstrates that respondents recognize both the benefits and limitations of privatization, reflecting a nuanced understanding of its role in shaping educational outcomes.

The descriptive results in Table 3 highlight widespread engagement in shadow education, with the highest mean for attending

private tutoring outside regular school hours. This aligns with extensive research showing that shadow education has become an institutionalized part of many educational systems, particularly in Asia and other competitive academic contexts (Bray, 2013; Byun & Park, 2012). High scores for exam-focused tutoring indicate an emphasis on performance over conceptual understanding, consistent with findings by Stevenson & Baker (1992) and Zhang & Bray (2020). Moderate perceptions of tutoring effectiveness and concerns about equity, time, and financial burden reflect the complex social implications of shadow education, as reported by Silova & Bray (2006) and Park & Byun (2015). Overall, the findings confirm that while shadow education is widely practiced and strategically valued for exam success, it also raises important considerations regarding fairness and educational quality. Table 4 shows that respondents hold moderate beliefs in meritocracy, recognizing personal effort and standardized assessments as important, but also acknowledging structural limitations such as the influence of social background. These findings are consistent with prior literature on meritocracy in education, which emphasizes that meritocratic ideals coexist with awareness of systemic inequalities (Young, 2019; Margolis, 2012). The relatively higher trust in entrance tests and standardized measures aligns with research suggesting that formalized selection systems are perceived as more objective, even if broader social inequities persist (Carnoy, 2017; Reay, 2017). Overall, the table reflects a cautious endorsement of meritocratic principles, highlighting a tension between fairness ideals and contextual realities within education systems.

The correlation analysis in Table 5 indicates significant positive relationships among privatization, shadow education, and meritocracy. The association between

privatization and shadow education is consistent with research showing that growth in private schooling often correlates with increased reliance on supplementary tutoring (Bray, 2013; Byun & Park, 2012). Similarly, the positive links between privatization and meritocracy, and between shadow education and meritocracy, reinforce studies suggesting that private initiatives and external tutoring can enhance academic performance and merit-based outcomes, albeit with equity implications (Verger et al., 2016; Park & Byun, 2015). These findings support the notion that privatization and shadow education are intertwined phenomena that collectively shape perceptions of meritocratic achievement.

Table 6 presents multivariate analysis confirming that privatization significantly affects both shadow education and meritocracy. The significant multivariate tests align with literature emphasizing the systemic impact of privatization on educational processes, demonstrating its influence on supplementary learning and merit-based outcomes simultaneously (Ball, 2012; Tooley & Dixon, 2006). The robustness of these findings across multiple multivariate criteria suggests a strong, consistent effect, reinforcing previous studies indicating that privatization is a key driver of educational change and student outcomes (Chung, 2019; Bray, 2013). Finally, Table 7 highlights the predictive influence of privatization on shadow education and meritocracy. The explained variance of 20% for shadow education and 32.2% for meritocracy suggests that privatization has a stronger impact on meritocratic practices than on tutoring reliance, consistent with research indicating that private sector growth is closely tied to academic selection mechanisms and performance-based evaluation (Lubienski & Lubienski, 2006; Verger et al., 2016). These findings reinforce the conclusion that privatization significantly shapes both students'

engagement in shadow education and perceptions of merit-based fairness within the education system, confirming trends observed in contemporary educational research.

Conclusion

The findings of this study indicate that privatization in the education sector significantly influences both students' engagement in shadow education and perceptions of meritocracy. The analysis shows that students frequently participate in private tutoring, highlighting shadow education as a prevalent and integral component of academic life. Privatization is positively associated with merit-based practices, suggesting that private institutions reinforce performance-oriented norms and emphasize achievement, which aligns with the broader goals of meritocracy. At the same time, while privatization enhances competition, responsiveness, and perceived academic quality, it raises important concerns regarding accessibility, affordability, and equity, particularly for students from lower socio-economic backgrounds. The descriptive and inferential results further reveal that students recognize the role of individual effort in academic success, but they are also aware that structural factors, such as family wealth and the quality of formal schooling, continue to shape educational outcomes. This reflects a nuanced perception of meritocracy, where respondents value personal effort yet acknowledges existing inequalities within the system. Overall, the study highlights that privatization, shadow education, and meritocracy are interrelated phenomena, creating both opportunities for academic advancement and challenges in achieving equitable education. These findings underscore the need for policies that balance quality, access, and fairness while supporting merit-based educational practices.

Recommendations

- Develop policies to regulate privatization in education to ensure equitable access for students from all socio-economic backgrounds.
- Increase investment and support in public schools to reduce reliance on private institutions and shadow education.
- Strengthen the quality of teaching in both public and private schools to minimize the need for excessive private tutoring.
- Introduce financial aid or subsidy programs to make private schooling and supplementary education more affordable for disadvantaged families.
- Implement standardized and transparent assessment systems to maintain merit-based practices while addressing social inequalities.
- Conduct awareness campaigns for parents and students about the role of shadow education and its balanced use.
- Provide training for teachers to adopt innovative pedagogical strategies that reduce dependence on private tutoring.
- Encourage collaboration between schools, parents, and local communities to ensure fair access to educational resources and opportunities.
- Regularly assess the impact of privatization and shadow education on student outcomes and social equity to inform policy adjustments.
- Promote further research on the long-term effects of privatization and shadow education on academic achievement and meritocracy.

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